

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Research Software Group

Advanced Research Computing

Annual Report 2025

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Advanced Research Computing

Advanced Research Computing (ARC) is the University of Birmingham's specialist team for computational- and data-intensive research. We design, build, and support services that enable world-class research across disciplines.

BEAR: Powering Research at Birmingham

Our flagship platform, the **Birmingham Environment for Academic Research (BEAR)**, provides secure data storage, high-performance computing, cloud resources, and expert support—much of it free at the point of use.

- Over **5,000 researchers and projects** rely on BEAR services.
- Since 2021, academics have reported **1,600+ publications** supported by BEAR.

BEAR is designed to make advanced computing accessible, helping researchers accelerate discovery and manage data effectively.

Baskerville: National Accelerated Compute

ARC also operates **Baskerville**, a national accelerated compute system funded by EPSRC and UKRI. Baskerville offers access to over 200 GPUs for AI and advanced modelling.

- In 2025, Baskerville supported researchers from Birmingham, the Baskerville consortium, and the wider UK research community.

- To date, **135 publications** have acknowledged Baskerville's contribution.

Our Team and Commitment

ARC is part of IT Services, led by **Carol Sandys** and reporting to the Chief Information Officer, **Mark Gee**. The team has grown substantially in recent years and now includes **40+ specialists**. The University of Birmingham's commitment to ARC was reaffirmed in the latest Vice Chancellor's Review of IT Services and in the University's Digital Strategy.

We work across three groups:

- **Architecture, Infrastructure & Systems Group**
- **Researcher Engagement & Data Group**
- **Research Software Group**

Together, these groups provide expertise in infrastructure, software engineering, data science and researcher support. We also collaborate with industry leaders like Lenovo to deliver sustainable, energy-efficient computing and invest in training to empower researchers with the skills they need for the future.

Looking Ahead

ARC continues to expand to meet the evolving needs of the research community, aligning with the University's Digital Strategy and Birmingham 2030 Strategic Framework ambitions.

This report introduces the work of the Research Software Group (RSG) and highlights case studies that demonstrate the impact of partnering with the RSG and ARC.

Research Software Group

The **Research Software Group (RSG)** is part of Advanced Research Computing at the University of Birmingham. Our mission is summed up in the words of the Software Sustainability Institute: “**Better software, better research.**”

Who We Are

Since its formation in 2017, the RSG has grown substantially. By the end of 2025, the team comprised **28 posts**, across four specialist roles:

- **Research Applications Specialists:** Support users of BEAR’s high-performance computing services—**BlueBEAR**, **BEAR Cloud**, and **Baskerville**. They install, curate, and maintain over **2,000 applications and libraries**.
- **Research Software Engineers (RSEs):** Join research projects for longer-term funded collaborations and provide **free advice, coaching, and coding support** for any University of Birmingham researcher.
- **Research Data Scientists (RDScis):** Deliver the **Research Data Science (RDSci) Service**, launched in 2023, working on grant-funded and pump-priming projects supported by the **Institute for Data and AI**.
- **DevOps Engineers:** Develop and maintain internal systems, tooling and automation and support applications deployed on BEAR Cloud virtual machines.

What We Do

- **Free and Funded RSE and RDSci Engagements:** Free advice sessions, short coding engagements, coaching for researchers. Longer collaborations can be funded by buying out time from our large team of RSEs and RDScis.
 - **BEAR Support:** Help with installing software, debugging, profiling, and optimising HPC jobs.
 - **Training:** Workshops on: Linux for HPC; coding in MATLAB, Python and R; AI and Deep Learning.
-

Our Purpose

The Research Software Group exists to:

- Enable the University of Birmingham's research community to get the best from their research software.
- Provide specialist software engineering and data science advice and support.
- Enhance the University's reputation for high-quality research.
- Maximise the return on the University's investment in BEAR.

For more details, visit the RSG web pages: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/rsg/>

Research Software Engineering Service

The Research Software Engineering Service (RSE Service) consists of a range of offerings to all researchers in the University. These services include advice, coaching, coding and mentoring sessions and engagements.

RSE Services are offered on a paid-for and a free basis. The paid-for services are usually funded through researchers' grants and allow for longer coaching or coding engagements, from one month to several years. Typical arrangements for funded engagements involve paying for a percentage of one or more RSEs to work on a defined project. The free services include one-off advice sessions, mentoring and short coaching or coding engagements.

More detail on our funded and free services can be found in the following sections and on our website: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/rsg/rse-service>.

RSE Service: Funded Coding

Our RSE Service allows researchers to add expert collaborators on to their projects.

- RSEs can be included on grants or funded from existing budgets.
- Engagements can be short (e.g. 3 months) to long (e.g. a few years).
- A typical RSE allocation is 50% FTE, which includes time from an additional senior RSE to provide code review, support, mentoring and advice throughout the project.

RSE Service: Free Coaching and Advice

- We also offer advice sessions, and short coaching engagements at no charge - subject to availability.
- Coaching to achieve a specific research software task, while also learning the skills to do it again in future.

The easiest way to get started with using the RSE Service is to send an email to our mailbox at bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk.

Research Data Science Service

Research Data Science Service

The **Research Data Science Service** is part of the [Institute for Data and AI \(IDAI\)](#) and the Research Software Group. Our mission is to enable and advance state-of-the-art data science research at the University of Birmingham through a range of complementary services. We are funded by both IDAI and the [Centre for Artificial Intelligence in Government \(CAIG\)](#).

Goals

The Research Data Science Service exists to:

- Facilitate data-intensive research by providing specialist data science support and advice.
- Help researchers increase the competitiveness of funding applications involving data science or AI.
- Support open science and reproducibility by helping researchers share data and code effectively.

Activities

Institute-Funded Work (Free at Point of Use)

- **Pre-award support:** advice on funding bids, project ideas, and preliminary data analysis (up to 2 days).
- **Post-award support:** publication health checks, reproducibility improvements (e.g., GitHub/GitLab versioning, Zenodo uploads), advice sessions (up to 2 hours).

- **Training:** bespoke workshops such as Advanced R and Data Carpentries (R for Social Sciences).
- **Collision-grant initiative:** £100k/year fund for short-term interdisciplinary research projects.

Grant-Funded Work

- Fund a Research Data Scientist for **10–50% FTE** on medium to long-term projects (> 4 weeks).
- Fund a Research Data Scientist for **50–90% FTE** on short-term projects (< 4 weeks).

Engagement types:

- **Data Science Coding:** implementing solutions (data prep, analysis, modelling, research).
- **Data Science Coaching:** advising on methods, best practices, and code review.
- Early involvement recommended for costing and bid preparation.

To find out more about the Service, please see <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/rsg/rdsci-service>.

messages and fix the installation issues. This means that our researchers can spend more time using the software for their research and less time grappling with installation issues.

HPC systems are complex, with the infrastructure that provides high-performance being significantly different to the environment most researchers are used to on their own computers. At the University, we use **EasyBuild** as the framework to install applications. This provides the team with a framework to easily maintain installations and an international community that works together to solve issues with installations. By doing this, we can ensure that the important libraries, such as those for mathematical operations and network communication, are working efficiently and effectively.

The team also maintain a suite of **ReFrame** tests, which both enables ARC to check the continuing performance of the HPC and to aid in debugging issues when there is a fault. By running thousands of short test jobs daily, we can be confident in the quality of the application stack provided to our research community.

We offer comprehensive technical support to the University's researchers, helping them use our systems effectively and efficiently. We also provide application-specific support and assist users in debugging problems.

The BEAR Apps team provides regular training to staff and research students from a variety of disciplines across the University as part of the wider BEAR Training programme.

We maintain our public-facing documentation sites (<https://docs.bear.bham.ac.uk> and <https://docs.baskerville.ac.uk>), which primarily contain technical documentation and apply to all the services provided to researchers. Additionally, we maintain our internal wiki pages to ensure knowledge is shared across the team.

Case Studies

Coding Case Study - Human-AI Interaction

Researchers

- Dr Marcus Perlman
- Dr Matteo Fuoli

Technologies

Django, Python, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Large Language Models (LLMs e.g. ChatGPT, Gemini, Llama)

Project Description

The Human-AI Interaction research team are exploring the language of trust in interactions between people and AI agents in different media, including text-based interactions, video chats, and virtual reality. Their research involves a series of pilot experiments using the 'trust game' paradigm widely used in behavioural economics. In this paradigm, a trustor decides how much money to send to a trustee. The sent amount is typically multiplied by the experimenter, and the trustee then decides how much of the multiplied amount to return. This method allows for the measurement of trust through tangible monetary decisions.

In their experiments, trustors have the opportunity to chat with their trustee prior to making their investment decision. In one condition, the trustor will communicate with a human trustee, and in another, with an AI agent. AI agents will be powered by large language models, trained and prompted to interact in various ways according to the variables the research team wish to test.

We've developed a web interface to allow the research team to run these experiments, which currently involve text-based conversations between humans and AI agents. The platform allows the research team to easily generate new experiments throughout the project. For each experiment they can choose an LLM from a University-approved cloud LLM platform, including the latest ChatGPT and Llama models. They can then tailor the behaviour of these LLMs for each experiment using customisable system prompts. The team can view and export the data generated from the experiments to use as part of their analysis, along with the data from the survey that participants complete at the end of each experiment.

Researcher Feedback

We worked with Michael Allaway and the Research Software Group to build a novel web interface to support our experiments on trust-building in human-AI conversation. Michael built us exactly what we were hoping for. He was always highly responsive to our feedback, and was clearly invested in doing his best to meet our specifications. We would be keen to enlist Michael's help in future developments of the project.

- **Dr Marcus Perlman**

Coding Case Study - Brain Tumour Invasiveness Prediction Using Deep Learning

Researchers

- Dr Vinton Cheng
- Dr Hamidraza Arjmandi
- Professor Vijay Sawlani

Technologies

Python, TensorFlow, Deep Learning, Autoencoders, BlueBEAR (HPC)

Project Description

Brain metastases are the most common malignant brain tumours. Currently, stereotactic radiosurgery (SRS) is the most effective way to tackle brain metastasis. However, approximately 20–40% of tumours recur after SRS, largely due to treatment failure at the brain metastasis edge. Dr. Vinton Cheng's research aimed to characterise the brain metastasis infiltration into the surrounding brain parenchyma using pre-clinical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans from tumour-bearing rats. The project began with the objective of developing a machine learning (ML) model to improve detection of the brain metastasis boundary on T1- and T2-weighted MRI sequences of rat brains, with the intention of subsequently applying this model to human datasets.

Initially, RSEs met with the research team to discuss potential methods for generating regions of interest (ROIs) from the T1/T2-weighted scans and their corresponding tumour and brain masks. In the first phase of the project, RSEs developed a custom

ROI Labelling Graphical User Interface (GUI) to streamline the process of creating ROIs around the tumour boundary and manually labelling them as invasive or non-invasive. This tool enabled researchers to efficiently generate the dataset required for training and testing the invasiveness prediction model.

The dataset presented challenges due to its limited size and the low resolution of each ROI. RSEs proposed solutions including biologically constrained upscaling and data augmentation. To address the paucity of training images, an auxiliary dataset of same-sized ROIs sampled from the entire brain was also prepared and used to train an autoencoder model to learn underlying feature representations. An invasiveness prediction model was then constructed using the parameter-frozen encoder combined with a classifier head trained on the ROIs labelled via the ROI Labelling GUI.

The project concluded with the handover of the source code for a Python package named `tumour_pipeline`, accompanied by relevant documentation and an end-to-end automated tumour invasiveness prediction pipeline. This pipeline supports dataset augmentation, pre-processing, and model training and testing on the University's HPC cluster, BlueBEAR.

Researcher Feedback

The support and input we received from Kiran and Adrian were invaluable for advancing the project and allowed us to develop a pipeline for processing the images to lay the foundation for the machine learning model. Having limited prior experience of machine learning algorithms, the insights offered by the RSE team enabled us to consider new ways to tackle problems such as managing low resolution images and relatively small datasets. The groundwork we have achieved over the course of the IDAI-funded project will facilitate our team to form partnerships with other groups so that we may expand the dataset and provide more robust training of the model developed by the RSE team.

- **Dr Vinton Cheng**

Coding Case Study - Nocturnal Oxygen Saturation as a predictor of Acute Mountain Sickness

Researchers

- Dr Kelsey Joyce
- Dr Kim Ashdown
- Dr Sarah Clarke
- The Birmingham Medical Research Expeditionary Society

Technologies

Python, MATLAB, machine learning/AI, SciKit, Slurm, HPC

Mountain view along the Everest trekking route

Project Description

Climbing Mount Everest has become one of the world's most iconic challenges, attracting thousands of trekkers each year. This feat carries significant risks, including developing Acute Mountain Sickness (AMS), a condition that can affect anyone ascending to high altitudes.

Dr Kelsey Joyce and her team, funded by The Birmingham Medical Research Expeditionary Society, have conducted a large-scale field study at several sites along the Everest Base Camp trekking route (pictured). Using pulse oximeters, they gathered physiological data of climbers while monitoring the prevalence of AMS.

Our team in the RSG has collaborated with Dr. Joyce to develop code that extracts key biomarkers from the raw data. These biomarkers, combined with metadata collected during the study, are now being used to train a machine learning model designed to predict the onset of AMS. The development of such a model would enable early preventive measures, such as medication or changes to ascent plans, ultimately improving safety and performance for climbers and researchers alike.

Researcher Feedback

The development of a predictive model for acute mountain sickness using non-invasive measures such as pulse oximetry is a massive breakthrough for high-altitude medicine. This work will have great impact in the field in terms of illness prevention, risk management, and overall experience for trekkers. The development of this predictive model has also established a strong foundation with scalable opportunities for future exploration in the high-altitude environment.

Working with the RSG Team was an incredibly delightful experience. I was repeatedly impressed by their expertise, professionalism and communication, collaborative problem-solving, and work rate. Partnering with the RSG Team has significantly accelerated our pipeline, which has allowed us to focus more deeply on the scientific interpretation, and also helped us to uncover patterns in the data that would not have been feasible on our own!

- **Dr Kelsey Joyce**

Coding Case Study - Clean Air 4V Phase 2

(INCHEM-Py) is a community-led box model that tracks the evolution and fate of atmospheric chemical pollutants indoors. MBM-Flex is designed to simulate air quality inside a number of interconnected rooms or an entire building. To do so, MBM-Flex runs a separate instance of INCHEM-Py for each room, and connects each instance with a new implementation of inter-room transport.

During this project, we fixed the most recent version of INCHEM-Py, because the open source offering was not compatible with Python 3.12 at the time. We made the integration between INCHEM-Py & MBM-Flex neater and more maintainable, we removed the

Researchers

- Dr Roberto Sommariva
- Professor Christian Pfrang

Technologies

Python, Javascript

Project Description

Exposure to air pollution is one of the greatest risks to human health, and it is indoors, where we spend upwards of 90 % of our time, that our exposure is greatest. The INdoor CHEMical model in Python

codependence of the two systems. We crucially changed the model to use an **unmodified** version of INCHEM-Py for each room, allowing for better decoupling between the codebases. We made use of standard techniques of graph theory in order to determine the paths through the building, more elegantly describing the advection between rooms. We improved the implementation of inter-room transport. This means we can now model the evolution of pollutants as they arise in rooms and then advect to spread throughout the whole building. Our ongoing work is to improve the user experience, depicting the interconnected rooms in a visual manner, and allowing the chemistry of the rooms to be entered using JSON formatted text.

Researcher Feedback

The RSG team has been working with us on an indoor air quality model (MBM-Flex), part of a project funded by the Clean Air Programme. The project is still ongoing, but we are very happy with the outcome: the code has been extensively re-factored to make it more efficient, faster, easier to maintain and use. The team was able to identify the main problems we were struggling with, and suggest creative solutions.

This work will ensure that MBM-Flex will be more widely adopted, and used in future research.

- **Dr Roberto Sommariva**

Coding Case Study - Citizen Science Monitoring of Birmingham Rivers

Researchers

Dr James White

Technologies

R Shiny, SQLite

Project Description

Birmingham River Champions is a pioneering citizen science initiative focused on assessing the health of Birmingham's highly urbanised rivers. This initiative empowers volunteers to collect and report data on various river ecosystem health metrics. In order to communicate data back to volunteers and evidence its impact, Dr. James White (the project lead) developed an R Shiny app alongside Charlotte Rush (University of Essex) that displayed how citizen science trends varied spatially and temporally. He approached the Research Software Group for support updating the application to prepare for its wider roll out to Rugby Borough Council and their local communities. Our team in the RSG worked with Dr. White to visualise water chemistry data and create a bespoke data collection survey form. In keeping with the collaborative nature of the project, the Shiny application has been converted into an R package available on GitHub, making it more easily available to more researchers and volunteers. Further, the package now includes a test suite and more extensive documentation.

Researcher Feedback

The RSG have made provided drastic improvements in the RShiny app that I developed to showcase river citizen science data back to volunteers collecting the data. Christine Stawitz, with support from Adrian Garcia, made invaluable suggestions on how my initial coding and the visualisation of the data could be enhanced in order to produce a better product for end users. By processing water chemistry data and creating a new survey form, volunteers can access all project resources in a single place, and is something that I had neither the time nor expertise to undertake. Christine and Adrian communicated progress every week and sought my preferences throughout in order to ensure the final deliverable met the needs of myself and local volunteers.

- **Dr James White**

Coding Case Study - Electricity Tariff Data Collection

Researchers

- Dr Grant Wilson
- Dr Edward Barbour

Technologies

Python, Prefect, Selenium web scraping, Streamlit

Project Description

Edward Barbour and Grant Wilson, Associate Professors in Chemical Engineering, explored detailed domestic heat pump demand data and became interested in their operational costs under different energy tariffs. They quickly discovered that tariff data was difficult to obtain and compare across different suppliers. With the help of the RSEs involved, they identified several key issues. Most suppliers require postcode and consumption estimates before showing prices. Some suppliers provide PDF-based data, which are difficult to extract and analyse due to format variability, while only Octopus Energy offers a usable API. Many suppliers provide a snapshot of prices rather than longitudinal dataset. In addition, some suppliers include VAT in their pricing data while others don't, and the same region is known by different names to different suppliers. Overall, the energy tariff data provided by electricity suppliers do not meet FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data principles, and the issues identified highlight a highly fragmented data landscape, making longitudinal research and policy analysis uncertain.

Despite challenges in this project, the RSEs involved collected electricity tariff data from multiple suppliers, using a combination of methods, including direct collection from Octopus API, Selenium-based web scraping, and data extraction from PDFs. They also developed a proof-of-concept visualisation tool to show tariff trends over time. The next step is to analyse the available data and present additional findings to Ofgem and to advocate for policy changes that improve data transparency and usability for the wider research community.

Researcher Feedback

As part of the GasNetNew project, we are seeking to understand the evolution of available electricity tariffs in the UK. However, the data collection process is challenging due to a fragmented data landscape and data coming in many different formats (APIs, information on websites, pdfs, etc.). Working with the Research Software Group (RSG) has greatly accelerated our data collection process, exploiting their expertise in web scraping and data parsing. This has delivered us a data collection pipeline which will be invaluable for future analysis of trends in electricity tariffs and we anticipate delivering exciting policy relevant results.

- **Dr Edward Barbour**

Coding Case Study – The Liver Inflammation Atlas: A Spatial Transcriptomics Exploration Platform

Researchers

- Dr Amber Bozward
- Professor Ye Oo
- Chiranjit Das

Technologies

R, Shiny, spatial transcriptomics (CosMx), plotly, BEAR Cloud VM, HPC

Project Description

Autoimmune and inflammatory liver diseases remain highly complex and poorly understood, in part because of the difficulty in visualising and interpreting high-resolution gene expression within damaged tissue. To help address this challenge, Professor Ye Oo, Dr Amber Bozward, and Chiranjit Das from the University of Birmingham are developing a new resource, The Liver Inflammation Atlas—a platform designed to integrate spatial transcriptomics datasets from human explant liver samples.

Our team collaborated with the researchers to deliver a standalone Shiny web application enabling interactive exploration of CosMx spatial transcriptomics datasets. The goal was to create an accessible, user-friendly interface where researchers could

search for genes of interest, visualise spatial expression patterns, examine cohort-specific variation, and explore cell-type composition across autoimmune hepatitis (AIH), seronegative fulminant hepatitis (SN), and donor control samples.

To support real-time interaction with millions of data points, extensive code restructuring, data wrangling and performance optimisation were required. The final application includes dynamically generated interactive UMAPs, boxplots, barplots, dotplots and heatmaps, alongside flexible filtering for gene, cohort, sample group and cell subsets. Significant effort was also dedicated to accessibility—improving colour palettes, keyboard navigation, focus order and screen-reader compatibility.

The current release of the website provides the first dedicated spatial atlas for autoimmune and inflammatory liver conditions, and establishes a scalable foundation for integrating additional datasets and modules.

Researcher Feedback

The process was extremely positive and straightforward. From the initial discussions through to deployment, the team were friendly, responsive, and proactive. They took the time to understand my scientific goals and then translated them into a technically robust, intuitive web application. I felt involved in each stage, and their ability to explain technical concepts in clear terms really helped.

What stood out most was how seamlessly the team integrated complex visualisation tools into a clean, accessible website. The platform allows users to query any gene of interest and immediately see its expression patterns across my datasets through boxplots, UMAPs, bar charts, and heatmaps. The visualisations are fast, interactive, and easy to interpret — exactly what I was hoping for.

I'd highly recommend working with the Advanced Research Computing team. They're technically brilliant, collaborative, and genuinely invested in helping researchers turn ideas into reality. The whole process was smooth, and the end product was exactly what I envisioned — and more.

- **Dr Amber Bozward**

Data Science Case Study - Ageing Brain Networks

Researchers

- Professor Fabian Spill
- Dr Enrico Amico

Technologies

Python, git, JupyterLab, cloud computing, large health database, data visualisation, neuroimaging analysis, statistical analysis

Project Description

The core focus of the project is to understand how the brain changes with age. The research team want to understand which data and methods are best suited to predict brain age and age-related disease.

The project started by exploring the concept of 'brain fingerprinting', which refers to identifying individuals by the unique patterns in their brain activity.¹ Using UK Biobank data (application number 516694), the Research Data Science team (RDSci) developed cloud-based workflows to analyse 2,800 participants that had functional MRI scans for two visits, recorded a few years apart. Typically, brain fingerprinting studies are performed on smaller samples sizes of a few hundred participants.² The RDSci team developed a Python library to perform data preparation, quality control and statistical analysis of these scans. Two functional

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.4135>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.4135>; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25089-1>; <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abj0751>

connectomes for each participant were created, representing how different areas of the brain are connected. Creating an “Identifiability Matrix”³ allows us to visualise how similar a participant is to themselves versus to other people, based on these functional connectomes.

In future, the research team is also interested in higher order brain network connectivity (going beyond connectivity between two pairs of brain regions).⁴

Researcher Feedback

Even though we already had pipelines for analysing brain fingerprints in my lab, I found it extremely valuable to work with the Research Data Science team to stress-test these workflows on truly large-scale datasets. Their independent expertise helped when dealing with more than 2,600 UK Biobank participants. To my knowledge, this is the first time brain fingerprinting has been demonstrated so robustly in a cohort of this size, and the RDSci support was instrumental in making that possible.

- **Dr Enrico Amico**

³ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25089-1>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-022-01852-0>; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54472-y>

Data Science Case Study - Simulating EU Council Deliberations

Researchers

Dr Christine Sheldon

Technologies

Python, multiagent systems, Autogen, GPT-4o-mini

Project Description

Deliberations within the Council of the European Union are central to EU policy-making. This project investigated whether LLM-based multi-agent systems can credibly model those negotiations to support governance research.

We built a Python library using Autogen to simulate Council debates given a user-specified list of participating member states and a short summary of the legislation under discussion.

To produce naturalistic exchanges, we fine-tuned GPT-4o-mini on excerpts sampled from Council debate transcripts and implemented custom turn-taking orchestration informed by published Council procedures and empirical analysis.

The Europa building is the seat of the European Council and Council of the European Union in Brussels

The annotated debate transcripts for this study were provided by the deliberations in the Council of the European Union (DICEU) project at University College Dublin.

Researcher Feedback

Working with a research data scientist allowed me to explore methodology that I would otherwise have had a hard time engaging with. Having expert support on the computational side expanded the scope of what I was able to do and strengthened the overall direction of the project.

- **Dr Christine Sheldon**

Data Science Case Study - Composer 2.0

own right, they provide a unique window onto the print trade of the eighteenth century.

In this project we used machine-learning models to clean and annotate the database, removing non-ornament images mistakenly included, and classifying the remaining ornaments into meaningful categories: headpieces, tailpieces and initials. The project makes this public database more useful to researchers around the world by increasing discoverability and reducing noise. In

Researchers

Dr Hazel Wilkinson.

Technologies

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Django, Python, PyTorch, TensorFlow

Project Description

Composer is a database of more than a million printers' ornaments from a library of eighteenth-century manuscripts. Ornaments provided thematic decoration to printed books, and were created by including carved woodblocks or arrangements of decorative metal type in the printing press. As well as being artistic creations in their

addition, it can be developed in multiple future directions, for example including more detailed, content-based annotations, and incorporating new data sources.

Researcher Feedback

Working with the RDSi and RSE team has transformed my project ahead of an application for major funding, by both making my data more accessible and discoverable, and forcing me to think about it critically in new ways

- **Dr Hazel Wilkinson**

Training

Each year, ARC delivers a variety of training courses to support researchers with the software they create and use, be that on their own systems or various tiers of HPC we support. These are organised by ARC's Researcher Engagement and Data Group (REDG) and delivered by a mixture of ARC staff and volunteers from across the University. In 2025, we delivered 32 courses to 532 researchers, with content ranging from the very first steps with writing software to advanced topics for experienced programmers.

Our long-running Introduction to Linux and Introduction to BlueBEAR courses give researchers the fundamental knowledge necessary to run their analyses on HPC facilities like BlueBEAR. These courses continue to run steadily at least once per term and are now joined by the Advanced BlueBEAR course, developed in 2024.

I liked that we actually submitted jobs so the scariest part is out of the way- at least now I know I won't accidentally break the entire HPC. (A participant on Intro to BlueBEAR)

The University is proud to be a Silver Member of [The Carpentries](#), a world-renowned programme of courses that teach foundational programming skills to researchers. Four more ARC team members qualified as instructors in 2025 and join the ten instructors already on our team.

We regularly teach Carpentries courses on Git, Python, R and MATLAB and have been adding new Carpentries and Carpentries-style courses to our programme. In 2024 we developed and started delivering the Image Processing in Python course, which ran twice in 2025 and we will continue to deliver in 2026. We also introduced courses on intermediate software skills like unit testing and packaging in both R and Python.

With the support of new funding from the University, we have begun a significant expansion of our courses in the new academic year. We have already delivered a new course in R and a new introductory course Introduction to Computational Thinking, in

response to feedback on existing courses. In addition, in 2026 we plan to redevelop the intermediate software skills course in Python and start to teach a Data Carpentries course on analysing geospatial data in Python.

Fantastic, clear, interactive and fun (A participant on Intro to Computational Thinking)

Our training programme has long included courses from NVIDIA's Deep Learning Institute, delivered by the RSG's NVIDIA University Ambassadors. There are currently three ambassadors, who have regularly taught the instructor-led courses Fundamentals of Deep Learning, Fundamentals of Accelerated Computing with CUDA Python and Fundamentals of Accelerated Computing with CUDA C/C++. Now that we've re-established these course following staff changes in ARC, we're looking forward to expanding our NVIDIA DLI programme in 2026 with new courses and new ambassadors.

He gave clear explanations in a nice moderate speed. He knew about recent developments in the field... (A participant on NVIDIA Fundamentals of Deep Learning, truncated).

2025 has been a year of continued growth for the BEAR Training programme that we hope to expand further in 2026. Our programme is guided by the needs of researchers at the University, so if you're interested in us developing material on a particular topic or delivering a course especially for your group, school, or other cohort, contact us.

Conferences and Events

BEAR Challenge

BEAR Challenge is an annual three-day event organised by the Advanced Research Computing team. It's aimed primarily at undergraduate students and provides them with hands-on experience using high-performance computing (HPC) resources to solve real-world problems. This year saw 15 teams (90 students) from a wide range of disciplines across the University register for the event and we set a new record for attendance. Each team was given access to a single node with four GPUs on Baskerville, our tier 2 HPC system.

There were five challenges set over the three days, each designed to test different aspects of HPC usage and problem-solving skills. The first day focused on familiarising participants with the Baskerville system and basic HPC concepts, where they had to create their team logo and navigate Bash and the terminal to submit Slurm jobs that performed MD5 hash cracking. The second day delved deeper, with challenges including the classification of galaxy images and the handling of massive datasets that meant

teams had to devise strategies to work within the constraints of the system's GPU limits. The final challenge, which took place on the third day, consolidated their experience of using Baskerville by getting them to design their own HPC cluster.

Across the three days were speeches from NVIDIA and Lenovo representatives, ARC staff and also talks from University of Birmingham researchers who use our HPC systems in their work. The final day also included a virtual tour of the data centre, with a further opportunity for the three highest-scoring teams to take a physical tour at a later date.

See the blog post <https://blog.bham.ac.uk/bear/2025/07/04/bear-challenge-2025/> for a full description of the event with responses and quotes from attendees.

CIUK Cluster Challenge Success

In an exciting follow-up to the event, two of the BEAR Challenge teams chose to participate in the national CIUK (Computing Insight UK) Cluster Challenge and one team ("Bearibles") successfully qualified to be one of the eight teams from across the UK that travelled to Manchester in December to compete in the finals at the CIUK 2025 conference. Gavin and Leo were also present to provide support and this team then went on to win the national CIUK Cluster Challenge competition, providing them with the opportunity to compete internationally by representing the UK at the International Supercomputing Conference (ISC) in Hamburg in 2026!

CIUK

Every year members of ARC go to Computing Insight UK. This event focusses on hardware and software of high-performance computers with presentations from users who show HPC usage in their work/research. Each year the event has a different theme and this year it was 'Computing Unites'.

Again, this year, during 'Day Zero' (the day before the main CIUK programme) there was the HPC-SIG / sysadmin technical meetup organised by Simon Attack and Ed and attended by several staff from ARC. There were six short talks, and two unconference sessions. The event proved very popular again this year, as demonstrated by the packed room.

CIUK is a great networking opportunity, with representatives of many ARC-like teams attending. To maximise this opportunity, ARC was involved in two stands in the research zone of the exhibition:

- Leo, Steph and Ed staffed the HPC-SIG stand, along with other HPC-SIG Executive Committee members, and handed out lots of HPC-SIG T-shirts and baseball caps.
- Gavin and James Carpenter were at the Baskerville stand to continue to promote Baskerville, meeting lots of current, previous and potential future users. Throughout the main two days all the members of ARC attending provided help and support on the stand.

A key benefit of the event is to network and maintain relationships with those in our industry. This led to meetings with representatives from Lenovo, NVIDIA, Intel, Alan Turing Institute, Rosalind Franklin Institute, EPCC/Archer2, RSE society, Software Sustainability Institute, Hartree and various tier 2 HPC providers. The team also met previous BEAR Challenge participants who have graduated and have careers related to high-performance computing.

10th EasyBuild User Meeting

Four members of the BEAR Apps team (James Carpenter, Chris, Gavin, and Simon Branford) travelled to Jülich, Germany in March 2025 to attend the 10th EasyBuild User Meeting. The annual EasyBuild User Meetings are a staple of the BEAR Apps Team's calendar, where the RSG have had a regular presence since 2017, with Simon now also being on the organising committee.

Simon presented at the event:

- EasyBuild 5.0, which introduced the recently released EasyBuild 5.0 to the community.

It was a great opportunity to interact with other members of the international EasyBuild community, particularly given the importance of the framework in the day-to-day maintenance of our HPC software stacks.

HPC-SIG

strengthening the group's outreach and engagement.

- **Steph** (leader of ARC's Researcher Engagement and Data Group) has also recently joined the HPC-SIG committee as EDIA Officer.

Community Engagement

Other members of the Research Software Group (and the wider ARC team) actively support HPC-SIG and regularly attend meetings. For example:

- **Simon Atack** (from ARC's Architecture, Infrastructure and Systems group) led two sessions at the HPC-SIG event in Strathclyde: 'Considering Direct Liquid Cooling?' and 'Summarising the Technical Meetup Breakout at CIUK 2024'.
- **Simon Atack** and **Ed** also led a meetup for technical staff to talk, learn & discuss important topics on 'Day Zero' of CIUK 2025.

The University of Birmingham is a long-standing member and active supporter of the HPC-SIG – the High Performance Computing Special Interest Group for UK Academia. HPC-SIG provides a national forum for sharing good practice, fostering collaboration, and influencing the future of HPC in UK research.

Leadership and Roles

- **Ed** serves as Chair of HPC-SIG, routinely leading meetings and facilitating discussions.
- **Leo** is the HPC-SIG's Communications Officer,

Why It Matters

HPC-SIG plays a vital role in:

- Sharing technical expertise and operational good practice.
- Discussing emerging technologies and sustainability in HPC.
- Building a collaborative HPC community in UK academia.

Our involvement ensures Birmingham remains at the forefront of UK HPC developments, contributing expertise and learning from peers across the academic community.

ISC High Performance 2025

Ed and Simon Branford attended ISC 2025, along with Jon and Rad from ARC's Infrastructure, Architecture and Systems team.

This was a great opportunity to talk directly to people from ARC-like teams from around the world, and find out what they are doing and planning for the years ahead.

Ed co-organised a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session for [HPC Communities](#). HPC Communities is an international collaboration founded by US Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC) and the UK High Performance Computing Special Interest Group (HPC-SIG).

RSE Midlands 2025

RSE Midlands is an annual one day event that brings together Research Software Engineers from around the Midlands. This is the fourth annual RSE Midlands event, and returned to the University of Birmingham (having been hosted by the Universities of Birmingham, Nottingham and Warwick previously). James Tyrrell, Gavin, Adrian and Matthew formed the organising committee with ARC funding their time to organise the event. The event was sponsored by Lenovo, Intel and the RSE society. The funds were used for the venue, food and merchandise. On the day Gavin MC'd the first half and led the group activity and James MC'd during the second half of the event. RSG members Matthew, Cat and Ed gave presentations throughout the event along with talks from the event's sponsors Intel and the RSE Society. There were two keynote speeches by Dr Grant Wilson and Dr Hazel Wilkinson, talking about their research and collaborating with our RSEs.

RSE Midlands 2026 will be in Nottingham and Gavin, James and Louise have formed a new organising committee with RSEs from the Universities of Nottingham and Warwick.

RSECon25

RSECon25 is this year's annual gathering of Research Software Engineers and those in adjacent fields from around the world. This year the conference was held at the University of Warwick and had the twin themes: RSE and Research Excellence; RSE as Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI).

During the conference there was a poster competition with Warrick presenting a poster on JOSS (The Journal of Open Source Software). This was both a presentation and a stand where people could come ask questions then vote on the best poster.

RSG members also assisted during sessions, with Neil chairing a session and Christine being a helper in the accessibility testing workshop. Some RSG members are part of special interest groups which have their own sessions during RSECon25. The regional RSE SIG (of which Gavin and James Tyrrell are members) ran a session led by Gavin and James presented on RSE

Midlands and took part in the Q&A panel. Gavin is also part of the HPC RSE SIG who had a full day session in which he chaired the training and community element. Alex Lyttle also joined the technical panel discussion during the HPC RSE SIG.

As part of our continued involvement in the wider RSE community Christine has joined the organising committee for RSECon26. James Tyrrell has been elected to the Board of Trustees for The Society of Research Software Engineering, where he holds the role of Vice-Treasurer. He is also the treasurer for RSECon26.

RSG Hackathon

The Research Software Group runs an annual internal hackathon as a knowledge-sharing and upskilling event. This is always a popular event, where members of the team get to work with colleagues that they may not otherwise interact with very much. Various different members of the group prepare sessions which usually take one or two days during the hackathon's two weeks. This year saw seven topics. The first was led by Simon Branford on the topic of working with continuous integration (CI) pipelines. Leo led both the second and fourth sessions covering a docstring linter and a team-coding effort creating a new API for one of our internal systems. Ed led the third session about good practice in code reviews. Gavin led the fifth session where attendees created videos using [asciinema](#) for HPC documentation. Cat and Chris led the sixth session, where the team collaboratively took up problems from the [Advent of Code](#), addressing the problems using programming languages they wanted to start learning or gain further experience in. The final session, led by James Tyrrell and Matthew, involved creating a set of resources to help RSEs and researchers, aiming to provide foundational knowledge and good practices with various domains and topics popular amongst RSEs.

STEP-UP RSLondon

This is a regional event for digital research technical professionals from London and the South East. A few members of ARC attended this event including James Tyrrell and Stephanie Thompson who gave a lightning talk. Gavin Yearwood was track chair for the

HPC and infrastructure section. He organised a team of reviewers and reviewed applications. On the day he was the session guide and chaired the first half of the HPC and infrastructure session.

Software Sustainability Institute Collaborations Workshop 2025

Rachael Stickland attended the Software Sustainability Institute's annual [Collaboration Workshop](#) in May 2025, as one of their 2025 SSI Fellows.

Charmed by Scotland and this collaborative environment, Rachael unexpectedly pitched an idea for the Hack Day and formed a team. The project aimed to expand the ways we can track and document diverse types of contributions to software-focused projects, beyond just coding contributions. Parts of this project have since been adopted by The Turing Way infrastructure group and are currently [under development on their GitHub](#).

Rachael contributed to a discussion about the role of AI in research software, which has been summarised in this blog post by other members of this discussion group: [Is AI After My Job? Navigating the Future of Research Software Engineering](#).

Contact Us

Research Software Group

For information about the Research Software Group, see <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/rsg>

For anything related to research software at the University of Birmingham, please email bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk

For anything related to research data science at the University of Birmingham, please email rdsci-team@contacts.bham.ac.uk

Advanced Research Computing

For information about Advanced Research Computing and the Birmingham Environment for Academic Research (BEAR), see <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear>

For general help or information about any BEAR service (BlueBEAR HPC, Research Data Store, ...) contact the team by email at bearinfo@contacts.bham.ac.uk

Check out the BEAR Blog at <https://blog.bham.ac.uk/bear>

Requests, Faults, Complaints

The IT Service Desk is your route to finding answers. Find all Advanced Research Computing items here: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear/sd/bear>

For all other IT Services items/help or to log faults and any complaints visit: <https://www.itservicedesk.bham.ac.uk/>